

Rac-3f

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-151-rac-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	1021
Vial:	82	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 151 rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	9.5 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/21/2021 10:07:04 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/21/2021 10:35:17 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.323	2836478	50.18	279083
2	7.658	2816358	49.82	223061

Asy-3f (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-154-1-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	1021
Vial:	83	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 154 1
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	9.5 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/21/2021 10:23:39 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/21/2021 10:36:55 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.327	1812606	6.90	180309
2	7.657	24448450	93.10	1925920